
**ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE COSTS AND CORPORATE
PERFORMANCE OF DEPOSIT MONEY BANKS IN NIGERIA**

EKUBIAT JOHN UDO (Ph.D)

**Department of Accountancy, School of Business and Management,
Akwa Ibom State Polytechnic, Ikot Osurua, Ikot Ekpene, Nigeria**

UWEM OKPOHO (Ph.D)

**Department of Banking & Finance, Faculty of Business Administration
University of Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria**

&

NKPODOT, UKEME CHARLES

**Department of Accountancy, School of Business and Management
Akwa Ibom State Polytechnic, Ikot Osurua, Ikot Ekpene, Nigeria**

ukeme_nkpodot@yahoo.com

+ 234 7035096419

Abstract

This study is an empirical study of Artificial Intelligence Costs and Corporate Performance of Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Nigeria. Ex-post facto research design was adopted in the study. The population was made up of the twenty-five (25) DMBs in Nigeria and sample size of 14 was selected based on the criterion that only this number of banks were fully listed and actively traded with NSE from January 01, 2011 to the December 31, 2021; which means that their 2011 to 2021 annual reports are accessible. Purposively sampling technique was adopted in the study to select the fourteen (14) sampled banks. The data were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics (multiple regression analysis). Results showed that Investment Costs in Artificial Intelligence Technologies – Robotic Technology (ATM costs being used as a proxy) has a significant negative influence on corporate performance (ROE); intelligent financial supporting systems (Hardware and software/intangibles assets costs) and Bank Network and Apps/POS costs both have positive significant influence on corporate performance (ROE). It was concluded in the study that artificial intelligence has significant joint positive influence on corporate performance (profitability, ROE). It was recommended in the study among others that, the deposit money banks in Nigeria should invest more on improved and more advanced artificial intelligence technologies such as POS, telebanking, internet banking, banking

apps, card data, smartcard/electronic purse and other electronic banking technologies that is void of incessant fraudulent activities, bank network failure, power challenge, security issues especially in some remote areas among others. Banks should stop investing more on ATMs because of the operational costs burden on the banks' profitability.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence Costs (AIC), Corporate Performance, Robotic Technology, ATM, Intelligent Financial Supporting Systems, Bank Network and APPS/POS, E-banking.

1 Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) in accounting and banking is one of the most importance benefits of science and technology in this 21st Century and the future as contributed by John McCarthy (1927 – 2011) popularly known as the Father of Artificial Intelligence. Artificial intelligence is considered the ability of a machine to imitate human actions like communication, decision-making, operations and handling of tasks among others. Some benefits of implanting Artificial Intelligence solutions, such as the possibility of obtaining more accurate results and time saving while processing a large amount of data are already known in different fields of activity. Artificial Intelligence in accounting solutions is not a new subject for researchers or a common practice for intellectual leading companies in technology but it is an interesting area of study recently due to its cost implications on the profitability, especially for their impact on the accounting and banking professions (Andriosopoulos *et al.*, 2019) and the post-COVID -19 lockdown of the entire world.

Dongre *et al.* (2020) opined that Artificial Intelligence plays greater roles in ordinary business activities in the areas of analysis and handling of documents in accounting and the uses of robotic technologies. Artificial intelligent automation is helpful in preparing payroll, bookkeeping, handling of daily routines, time savings, speed, reduces monotonous responsibilities, and increasing higher level of accuracy. The authors added that Artificial Intelligence technology will enhance several business accounting's processes to include procurement and purchasing, invoicing, purchase orders, expense reports, accounts payable and receivables among others. It can also improve fraud detection through more sophisticated machine learning model of normal activities and better prediction of fraudulent activities in the firm as well as reducing the operational costs and barriers of doing business and improves firms' performances.

Moreso, in the banking sector, artificial intelligence technologies can help to store banking data for a long time and easily access banking work, it can design Mc-excel in that way which supports accounting activities such as budgeting, preparing financial statements and routine reports, improve workplace communication with the help of them the organization personnel easily understand their work this will lead to increase productivity. To the health care sector, artificial intelligence can assist to maintain the records and accounts of every patient as well as helps to improve reliability, predictability, consistency of the pharmaceutical work.

Following the failure of businesses in the 2000's, about 60% to 94% of firms in US have embraced AI, especially, the banking sector and many more organizations have therefore directed towards the more application of science and technology such as Artificial Intelligence in their activities, accountancy profession is not in exception. Although the application of Artificial Intelligence in accounting and finance looks positive to the increasing of efficiency in organizations, it seems that the firms might ignore monitoring the costs and updates required for accounting intelligent systems to avoid any risk and uncertainty (Gotthardt *et al.*, 2019). Moreso, some firms and even industries may lack the understanding of how Artificial Intelligence techniques can improve corporate operations and what appropriate accounting system to decrease Artificial Intelligence operation risks. This raises some doubts about the usefulness of this technology and allows companies to have concerns about whether adopting AI is worth it or not (Nickerson, 2019). Thus, it can be argued that the existence of AI itself may change the workload of accountants and auditors and increase their efficiency and effectiveness as well as aids bankers in financial analyses and agencies (Solaimani *et al.*, 2020) while others opined of the high costs burden of AI costs on banks' profitability.

Recently, some firms used robotic technology having an intelligent machine to perform a complete task without the use of human assistance such as Automated Teller Machine (ATM), banking apps, Point of Sale (POS) among others in most banks, Aluminum Smelting Companies, Coal Mining Companies, drones for security firms and agents, industrial manipulator arm (unimate), supercomputer for predictions and budgeting, security robots such cobalt, self-driving cars, telepresence robots that allow one to be present at a place without actually going there, aquanaut, diving humanoid among others. Also, in today's business, Natural Language Processing (NLP) provides computers with the ability to understand and interpret human language, written or spoken. How difficult a task it is, one can tell by observation of AI that look at

things like humans, computer vision and security could analyze images. Nowadays, documents, videos, and images can be analyzed by AI as well. The pace of AI innovation is both exciting and costly. Some firms may not deploy these AI technologies, simply because, it is too costly to run it. But advocates of AI in accounting and finance believe that the gains from running them will in a long -run outweigh the costs of running them.

However, over the years, studies undertaken on AI in accounting and finance were aimed at examining what is the correct way to start Artificial Intelligence adoption in firms; Meservy *et al.* (1992) examined the application of artificial intelligence in accounting, tax and audit services using expert/decision support system, simulation model as artificial intelligence technologies. Some authors examined the importance, opportunities, risks challenges of artificial intelligence (such as Bizarro and Dorian, 2017; Dongre *et al.*, 2020; Stancu and Duțescu, 2021); other researchers such as Zhang *et al.* (2020) holistically reviewed of recent developments in AI, Big Data and Machine Learning, exploration of the evolution of accounting profession faced by various technological advancement, examination of inherent hurdles and opportunities of new technologies posed in front of accounting professionals and pedagogy using the machine and deep learning, artificial general intelligence, blockchain technology, robotic process automation, radio frequency identification (RFID), speech recognition - natural language processing, artificial neural networks as the artificial intelligence technologies.

Whereas some authors examined the relationship of Artificial Intelligence between artificial intelligence (AI) and corporate accounting operations (Solaimani *et al.*, 2020) and authors such as Odoh *et al.* (2018) examined impact of artificial intelligence in accounting (investment in AI being a proxy) on the performance of accounting operations among accounting firms. But of all the studies, none has holistically examined the influence of artificial intelligence and the corporate performance in relation to the various cost components involved in artificial intelligence in accounting and finance (intellectual technologies – robotic technology (such as ATM), intelligent financial supporting systems (such as Hardware and software/intangibles assets) as well as bank network and apps and the financial performance in terms of return on equity (ROE). Therefore, this study sought to examine this problem.

The main objective of the study is to examine Artificial Intelligence Costs and Corporate Performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. The specific objectives include, to:

- i. examine the influence of robotic technology (RT) costs on Corporate Performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria in terms of return on equity (ROE).
- ii. evaluate intelligent financial supporting systems (IFSS) costs impact on Corporate Performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria in terms of return on equity (ROE).
- iii. assess how bank network and apps as well as POS affect Corporate Performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria in terms of return on equity (ROE).
- iv. determine the joint influence of Artificial Intelligence costs (Robotic technology, intelligent financial supporting systems as well as bank network and apps/POS) on Corporate Performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria in terms of return on equity (ROE).

The following Null Hypotheses were framed in line with Specific Objectives of the study:

- H₀₁:** Robotic technology (RT) costs do not significantly influence Corporate Performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria in terms of return on equity (ROE).
- H₀₂:** Intelligent financial supporting systems (IFSS) costs do not significantly impact Corporate Performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria in terms of return on equity (ROE).
- H₀₃:** Bank network and apps costs do not significantly affect Corporate Performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria return on equity (ROE).
- H₀₄:** There is no significant joint influence of Artificial Intelligence costs (Robotic technology, Intelligent financial supporting systems as well as bank network and apps) on Corporate Performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria return on equity (ROE).

2 Review of Related Literature

In this Section, the related literature were reviewed in three viewpoints as; conceptual review, theoretical framework and empirical review of literature.

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Artificial Intelligence

Artificial Intelligence is the ability of a digital computer or a robot technology

to do accounting and finance and other difficult tasks that are usually done by humans due to the fact that the tasks require human intelligence and discernment or intelligence beings. AI is term that describes technology mimicking human processing capabilities. Artificial intelligence costs involve the expenditure incurred or investment in the provision of Artificial Intelligence technologies. Intelligent financial supporting systems (IFSS) is also called financial technologies set up to ensure provisions of financial services to unbanked population. It involves the way technologies are used to make money changes hand in financial transactions such as online shopping, ticket purchases and payments for goods and services, internet banking, debit and credit cards banking through the use of bank's internet network (Oriobe & Akinyede, 2017).

Some common applications of Artificial Intelligence technologies in the banking sector include:

(i) Customer service/engagement (Chatbot): Chatbots deliver a very high return on investment (ROI) in cost savings, making them one of the most commonly used applications of AI across industries. Chatbots can effectively tackle most commonly accessed tasks, such as balance inquiry, accessing mini statements, fund transfers, etc. This helps reduce the load from other channels such as contact or enquiry centres, internet banking among others.

Chatbots, facial recognition, and natural language processing (NLP) make banking apps easier to use, improving customers satisfaction. AI in banking can help automate and improve customer-facing operations. the Chatbot can answer financial questions, help customers make payments and assist more users without needing more staff. This will serve their clients at any time despite potential worker shortages. This improved accessibility helps banks provide higher customer satisfaction and generate loyalty.

(ii) Robo Advice: Automated advice is one of the most controversial topics in the financial services space. A robo-advisor attempts to understand a customer's financial health by analyzing data shared by them, as well as their financial history. Based on this analysis and goals set by the client, the robo-advisor will be able to give appropriate investment recommendations in a particular product class, even as specific as a specific product or equity.

(iii) General Purpose/Predictive Analytics: One of Artificial Intelligence's most common use cases includes general-purpose semantic and natural

language applications and broadly applied predictive analytics. Artificial Intelligence can detect specific patterns and correlations in the data, which legacy technology could not previously detect. These patterns could indicate untapped sales opportunities, cross-sell opportunities, or even metrics around operational data, leading to a direct revenue impact.

(iv) Cybersecurity: Artificial Intelligence (AI) can significantly improve the effectiveness of cybersecurity systems by leveraging data from previous threats and learning the patterns and indicators that might seem unrelated to predict and prevent attacks. In addition to preventing external threats, AI can also monitor internal threats or breaches and suggest corrective actions, resulting in the prevention of data theft or abuse.

(v) Credit Scoring/Direct Lending: Artificial Intelligence (AI) is instrumental in helping alternate lenders determine the creditworthiness of clients by analyzing data from a wide range of traditional and non-traditional data sources. This helps lenders develop innovative lending systems backed by a robust credit scoring model, even for those individuals or entities with limited credit history. AI covers a wide range of technologies, including machine translation, chatbots and self-learning algorithms, all of which can allow individuals to better understand their environment and act accordingly. Organizations have been adopting AI technological innovations with a view to adapting to or disrupting their ecosystem while developing and optimizing their strategic and competitive advantages (Wamba-Taguimdje *et al.*, 2020).

2.1.2 Corporate Performance

Corporate performance as relates to accounting and finance involves to the level of success or failure in terms of financial performance indices. According to Mutende *et al.* (2017), financial performance refers to a firm's ability to achieve planned financial results as measured against its intended resources. The concept of banks' financial performance has to do with the level of success or failure of a bank in monetary terms. Generally, the common financial indices and ratios used in measuring banks' financial performance are revenue growth, return on equity, return on assets, profit margin, sales growth, capital adequacy, liquidity ratio, return on deposits (ROD), net interest margin (NIM), profit expense ratio (PER) and stock prices. Banks' performance is mostly evaluated in terms of profitability since it measures the efficiency of the managers and the firms' returns/profit for their investors. Profitability ratios or measures therefore provide an insight to the degree of success in achieving this primary objective (Idekulim, 2014). The most common profitability measures or ratios

are return on capital employed (ROCE), gross profit margin, net profit margin, return on equity (ROE) and return on assets (ROA).

In summary, ROCE measures the overall returns from all investments. Gross profit margin measures the proportion or percentage of sales revenue earned as profit after deducting cost of sales only, whereas net profit margin measures the proportion or percentage of sales revenue earned as profit after deducting all expenses except interest and tax. The operational performance of a business should be considered from the perspective of net profit and not gross profit margin. Return on equity (ROE) indicates the extent of profit on equity shareholding investment based on profit, while return on assets (ROA) is the extent of profit earned on every N1 invested on or utilised of total assets. ROA is sometimes called return on total assets. ROA is a measure of firms' performance that takes into consideration total assets or all capitals in the generation of the firms' profitability or returns. ROE is considered and used in this study because banks are financed by shareholders' funds/equity. Previous researches like those of Ifrueze *et al.* (2014) as well as Talan *et al.* (2017) have claimed that the profitability of firms could be affected the level of investment in infrastructures. Profitability is the financial matrix that indicates firms' ability to make enough incomes to cover its expenditures and operational costs during the operational period. The ability to make sufficient profit is the primary objective of every business, therefore, providing an insight to the level of performance. In other words, this is a company's capability of generating profits from its operations. Odoh *et al.* (2018) found that profitable firms in Nigeria are due to efficient investment on artificial intelligence (AI) and that the investment in artificial intelligence have significant impact on the return of equity of banks.

Evaluation of financial performance of banks entails x-raying the position of the banks by their profitability and efficiency. The profitability is the main index of a firm's performance. Banks have a peculiar type of financial indicators and therefore, the rate of profitability is very important to their performance. The performance can be divided into two elements: profitability and efficiency, which are interrelated in one way or another (Tahir, 1999). Thus, studies of profitability and efficiency of banks are important indices which contribute to the improvement of the banks' performance, the evaluation of banks' operations and the determination of management planning. Also, research on banks' performance is important for the improvement of the economy due to the fact that banks contribute to economic growth.

Given that the fundamental objective of a firm’s business activity is that of generating profit for shareholders and other stakeholders, ROE best suits this purpose and is relevant in assessing performance. It reveals the rate of profit earned from an investment by shareholders and related investors (Epps and Cereola, 2008). It is a measure of the capacity of investment by shareholders to yield revenue in excess of what has been invested. Return on equity (ROE) usage as the dependent variable in this study is because it determines the extent of efficiency of the banks’ management in using shareholders’ investments. It indicates profit for the year obtained from operations in relation with equity contributed by shareholders. It is computed as:

ROE = Profit for the year / Total Equity.

2.1.3 Artificial Intelligence (AI) Impact on Firms Performance

Artificial Intelligence (AI) saves time and money by automating and optimizing routine processes and tasks. It increases productivity and operational efficiencies, make faster business decisions based on outputs from cognitive technologies. Artificial Intelligence (AI) allows managers to consider AI not as a single technology but as a set/combination of several different configurations of IT in the various company’s business areas because multiple key elements must be brought together to ensure the success of AI: data, talent mix, domain knowledge, key decisions, external partnerships, and scalable infrastructure. IA also improves business processes such as meetings, enhancing sales and marketing, customer service, product development processes, automating content generation, the manufacturing process and refining recruitment. IA can help address regulatory compliance, manage risks and detect fraud.

The aim of the study is to provide empirical evidence regarding Artificial Intelligence (AI) costs implication on the financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. This association is demonstrated in the conceptual model specified in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework, *Developed by Researchers (2022)*

2.2 Theoretical Framework

Contingency Theory: This theory was propounded by Fred Edward Fiedler in 1964. A contingency theory is an organisational theory that states that there is no best way to organize a corporation, a company, or to make decision than effective and efficient management and investment in its resources. This theory provides a realistic view of management and organisation of the deposit money banks DMBs in Nigeria. contingency theory is beneficial to DMBs because of the potential for learning from specific situations and using these lessons to influence future management of the same or similar situations. The ability to adapt external pressures and changes is also an advantage. The theory will help the managers to react quickly to the changes and resolving problems, it also gives them significant discretion in their decision-making and profit-orientation.

2.3 Empirical Review

Agarwall *et al.* (2021) examined Artificial Intelligence (AI) as the digital technology that must be brought together to facilitate enhanced performance of business organizations. The study aims at a pilot study to assess the influence of AI on the operating performance of the companies and thereby fills the gap in the existing literature. This paper aims at establishing the relationship and exploring the influence of artificial Intelligence on operational performance of companies in different sectors in India. An attempt has been made to assess the difference in operational performance in pre and post AI era. In the study, the artificial Intelligence is measured by the variables such as computer hardware and intangibles (computer software etc.). The operating profit and operating cost have been taken as the proxy variables for operational performance of companies. The study was based on secondary data which has been collected from annual reports of sample companies. The sample companies under study comprise of manufacturing, telecommunication, and IT companies for the time period from the year 2004 to 2018. The statistical software including Ms. Excel and EViews 10 have been used to run the t-test and panel regression model for statistical inferences. The study found that artificial Intelligence has a significant influence on companies operating cost as well as operating profit.

Odoh *et al.* (2018) examined the effect of artificial intelligence on the performance of accounting operations among accounting firms in South East Nigeria. Descriptive research design was adopted in the study among 185

accountants and managers in accounting firms in Anambra and Enugu State. Structured questionnaire was used to obtain the information needed for the study. Data collected were presented in table. The study hypotheses were tested using linear regression at 5% level of significance. The result of the study showed that Expert system ($r = 0.904$; $F = 608.447$; $p = 0.000$) and Intelligent agent ($r = 0.754a$; $F = 178.810$; $p = 0.000$); has a significant effect on the performance of accounting function of accounting firms in South East Nigeria. It was concluded that, the application of artificial intelligence positively influences the performance of accounting functions. The researchers recommended that accountants and accounting firms should continually improve their knowledge regarding artificial intelligence as this will enhance the performance of accounting functions, thereby eliminating certain accounting cost.

Wamba-Taguimdje *et al.* (2020) investigated the influence of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on firm performance, notably by building on the business value of AI-based transformation projects. The research process deployed included responding to the research question, making discussions, interpretations and comparisons, and formulating recommendations. It was based on a review of 500 case studies from IBM, AWS, Cloudera, Nvidia, Conversica, Universal Robots websites among others. Studying the influence of AI on the performance of organizations, and more specifically of the business value of such organizations' AI-enabled transformation projects, required us to make an archival data analysis following the three steps, namely the conceptual phase, the refinement and development phase, and the assessment phase. The results of our study have highlighted such AI benefits in organizations, and more specifically its ability to improve on performance at both the organizational (financial, marketing and administrative) and process levels. Through working on the AI attributes, organizations can therefore enhance the business value of their transformed projects. The same results also showed that organizations achieve performance through AI capabilities only when they use their features/technologies to reconfigure their processes.

3 Methodology

Ex-post facto research design was used in the study. It is also referred to as causal-comparative design. The design was considered best for the study as it allows for the use of existing data as well as not permitted the control and

manipulate of variables since the subjects were selected on the basis of naturally occurring characteristics. The study’s population was made up of the twenty-five (25) deposit money (consolidated) banks. The selection of this population was due to the fact they were listed and actively traded as at January 01, 2011 to December 31, 2021 and the sector deployed the highest number of artificial intelligence technologies for value and wealth creation during the booming of the universal banking. The DMBs were also noted for laying-off members of staff who the management felt were not adding value to the bottom line in order to reduce costs and also because of the deployment of artificial intelligence (AI). The list of the Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria as at January 01, 2011 - December 31, 2021 is showed in Table 1.

Table 1: List of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria As At Jan. 01, 2011 - Dec. 31, 2021

S/N	BANK @ January 01, 2011	BANK @ December, 2021	REMARK/CRITERIA	SAMPLE
1.	Access Bank	Access Bank	Stock Actively traded on NSE	Qualify
2.	Afribank	Main Stream Bank	Stock NOT Actively traded	NOT Qualify
3.	Diamond Bank	Diamond Bank	Stock Actively traded on NSE	Qualify
4.	EcoBank	EcoBank	Stock Actively traded on NSE	Qualify
5.	Equatorial Trust Bank	Sterling Bank acquired	Stock NOT Actively traded	NOT Qualify
6.	First City Monument Bank (FCMB)	Merged with FINBANK	Stock Actively traded on NSE	Qualify
7.	Fidelity Bank	Fidelity Bank	Stock Actively traded on NSE	Qualify
8.	First Bank Plc	First Bank Plc	Stock Actively traded on NSE	Qualify
9.	First Inland Bank	Merged with FCMB	Stock NOT Actively traded	NOT Qualify
10.	Guaranty Trust Bank (GTB)	Guaranty Trust Bank (GTB)	Stock Actively traded on NSE	Qualify

11.	IBTC-Chartered Bank	IBTC-Bank	Stanbic	Stock traded	NOT	Actively	NOT Qualify
12.	Intercontinental Bank	Intercontinental Bank		Stock traded	NOT	Actively	NOT Qualify
13.	Nigeria International Bank	Nigeria International Bank		Stock traded	NOT	Actively	NOT Qualify
14.	Oceanic Bank	Acquired by EcoBank		Stock traded	NOT	Actively	NOT Qualify
15.	Key Stone Bank	Former Platinum Bank (Nationalized)		Stock traded	NOT	Actively	NOT Qualify
16.	Polaris Bank	Former Skye Bank		Stock on NSE	Actively	traded	NOT Qualify
17.	Heritage Bank	Former Spring Bank		Stock traded	NOT	Actively	NOT Qualify
18.	Stanbic Bank	Now Stanbic Kank	IBTC-	Stock traded	NOT	Actively	NOT Qualify
19.	Standard Chartered Bank	Standard Chartered Bank		Stock traded	NOT	Actively	NOT Qualify
20.	United Bank Africa	United Bank of Africa		Stock on NSE	Actively	traded	Qualify
21.	Sterling Bank	Sterling Bank		Stock on NSE	Actively	traded	Qualify
22.	Union Bank	Union Bank		Stock on NSE	Actively	traded	Qualify
23.	Unity Bank	Unity Bank		Stock on NSE	Actively	traded	Qualify
24.	Wema Bank	Wema Bank		Stock on NSE	Actively	traded	Qualify
25.	Zenith Bank	Zenith Bank		Stock on NSE	Actively	traded	Qualify

From the total population of the study of twenty-five (25), the number that meet the specification and requirement for the study was fourteen (14) banks. This is due to the fact that only these fourteen (14) banks were fully listed and actively

traded with NSE beginning from 2011 to the ending of December 2021; which means that their 2011 to 2021 annual reports are accessible. Purposively sampling technique was adopted in the study. Purposive sampling technique was applied in the research to select the fourteen (14) sampled banks. This technique was used on the basis of the easiness with which the data can be collected from the banks’ websites and data banks and having met the criteria of actively traded listed banks. The period from 2011 to 2021 was used based on the fact that the prior years of the sampled banks, some financial and non-financial information were not available due to non-trading of active stocks or delisting by NSE. Secondary sources of data were used and consisted of the annual reports and accounts of the selected listed banks and formed the main sources of data used in this study. Specifically, data were sourced from directors’ reports, Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN), Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Bullion/Reports, NSE financial statements and Fact book and compliance reports.

In order to test the research hypotheses, multiple regression models (functional form, econometrical form and conceptual model equation) were used:

$$FP_{it} = f(AI_{it}) \quad \text{--- Functional Relationship Equation}$$

$$Y_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 X_{1it} + \alpha_2 X_{2it} + \alpha_3 X_{3it} + \alpha_4 X_{4it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad \text{--- Econometric Equation}$$

$$ROE_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \text{LogRT}_{it} + \alpha_2 \text{LogIFSS}_{it} + \alpha_3 \text{LogBNA}_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad \text{--- Conceptual Model Equation}$$

- Where; AI = Artificial Intelligence costs
 ROE = Returns on Equity
 RT (X₁) = Robotic Technology (RT) [ATM costs being a proxy]
 IFSS (X₂) = Intelligent financial supporting systems (IFSS) [Hardware and software/intangible assets costs being a proxy]
 BNA (X₃) = Bank network and apps costs as well as POS.
 ε = Error Term

4 DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Table 2: Level of Investment in RT, IFSS, BNA and ROE in the Selected DMBs

S/N	DMBs	n	RT		IFSS		BNA		ROE	
			Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
1	Access	11	21.44	12.18	0.44	0.24	1.19	0.59	0.12	0.04
2	Diamond	11	18.23	6.44	0.49	0.24	0.64	0.24	0.06	0.10
3	Eco bank	11	20.58	10.19	0.35	0.20	0.41	0.22	2.13	0.98
4	FCMB	11	16.80	4.67	0.61	0.34	0.05	0.03	0.05	0.06
5	Fidelity	11	17.81	6.35	0.43	0.14	0.42	0.21	0.04	0.04
6	First	11	62.75	26.12	2.42	1.11	0.30	0.16	0.09	0.06
7	GTB	11	18.83	3.13	0.67	0.12	0.93	0.90	0.24	0.06
8	Skye	11	14.55	2.69	0.66	0.45	0.34	0.18	0.17	14.46
9	Sterling	11	8.64	2.72	0.76	0.42	0.36	0.35	0.08	0.18
10	UBA	11	34.22	7.85	1.40	0.33	0.80	0.44	0.12	0.10
11	Union	11	28.46	2.37	1.14	0.54	0.49	0.48	-0.19	0.49
12	Unity	11	14.14	4.03	0.57	0.24	0.15	0.11	0.49	2.43
13	Wema	11	6.94	1.55	0.62	0.13	0.38	0.26	-0.49	1.41
14	Zenith	11	44.20	11.41	2.65	0.50	1.74	1.21	3.59	0.06

RT – Robotic Technology, IFSS - Intelligent Financial Supporting Systems, BNA - Bank Network and Apps Costs, ROE- Return on Equity. Note: RT, IFSS and BNA are in millions.

Result in Table 2 presents the level of RT, IFSS, BNA and ROE of the selected 14 Deposit Money banks. Based on the mean values, First Bank Plc reported the highest mean values of RT (62.75 million), IFSS (2.65 million), Zenith bank reported the highest BNA (1.74 million) and the highest in ROE (3.59). Result also shows that the least investments by the banks and the profitability level in terms of RT, IFSS, BNA and ROE were reported by Wema bank (6.94 million), Ecobank (0.35 million), Wema bank (0.08 million) and Wema bank (-0.49) respectively.

Table 3: Regression summary showing the influence of AI costs on Profitability of listed DMBs in Nigeria

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	0.799	0.658	0.641	0.1797525	1.97622

Source: Authors' Computation (2022) using SPSS Version 20.0

Table 3 is the presentation of the summary result of the influence of Artificial Intelligence (AI) costs on profitability of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. Results show R-Square (R²) of 0.658, which means that 65.8% of the variation in the profitability (ROE) of listed deposit money banks was accounted for by investment in Artificial Intelligence (AI) as measured by RT, IFSS and BNA. To examine whether there is presence of autocorrelation, the Durbin Watson test was used and the result yielded Durbin Watson statistic of 1.97622 was obtained which is greater than 1 and less than 3.00 meaning that there is no evidence of autocorrelation. Result of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) showing whether there is a regression variability between the dependent variable (profitability as measured by ROE) and Artificial Intelligence (RT, IFSS and BNA) is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: ANOVA result summary of ROE, RT, IFSS and BNA of the selected listed deposit money banks in Nigeria

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-calc.	F-crit.	p-value
1 Regression	841.285	4	210.321	20.802	2.43	0.001
Residual	1506.513	149	10.111			
Total	2347.798	153				

Source: Researchers' Computation (2022) using SPSS Version 20.0

From the ANOVA result presented in Table 4, the F-calculated of 20.802 was obtained with F-critical of 2.43 with p-value of 0.001. The F-calculated is greater than the critical F-value which means that the independent variables (RT, IFSS and BNA) are the Artificial Intelligence significantly responsible for the variation responsible for the variation in the dependent variable (ROE). This result also signifies that the regression model of ROE with RT, IFSS and BNA (AI) costs was statistically adequate to jointly predict the ROE (corporate performance).

Table 5: Coefficients of the regression ROE with RT, IFSS and BNA of Listed DMBs in Nigeria

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-calc.	p-value	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	0.519	6.593		0.079	0.937		
1 RT	-2.496	0.938	-0.181	-2.661	0.009*	0.929	1.077
IFSS	1.499	0.353	0.333	4.244	0.000*	0.699	1.430
BNA	1.068	0.355	0.256	3.009	0.003*	0.596	1.679

Source: Researchers' Computation (2022) using SPSS Version 20.0

In Table 5, the regression coefficients for the model parameters were computed showing the influence of Artificial Intelligence costs on profitability (ROE) of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. The result shows that as Robotic Technology (ATM) costs ($\beta = -0.181$, Std Error = 0.938, t-calc = -2.661 and p-value = 0.009) has a negative significant influence on profitability (ROE). This means that as RT increases, ROE decreases and vice versa. But IFSS costs ($\beta = 0.333$, Std Error = 0.353, t-calc = 4.244 and p-value = 0.000) and BNA Costs ($\beta = 0.256$, Std Error = 0.355, t-calc = 3.009, and p-value = 0.003) all have positive significant influences on profitability (ROE). This implies that as IFSS and BNA increase, ROE increases and vice versa. The result also reveals standardised beta coefficient of -0.181, for RT, which implies that if other variables are held constant, for every N1 increase in Robotic Technology (ATM) costs, the profitability (ROE) of the listed DMB in Nigeria will decrease by N0.181. It was also found that the standardised beta coefficient of 0.333 for IFSS and 0.256 for Bank network and apps (BNA). These imply that if other variables are held constant, for every ₦1 increase in IFSS and BNA, the profitability (ROE) of the listed DMB in Nigeria will increase by N0.333 and N0.256 respectively. The result also reveals tolerance of 0.929, 0.699 and 0.596 for RT, IFSS and BNA and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) of 1.077, 1.430 and 1.679 respectively as a check for the possible presence of multicollinearity. The tolerances were all greater than 0.1 while VIFs were all less than 10 indicating that there is no evidence of multicollinearity.

In summary, the predicted model is:

$$ROE_{it} = 0.519 - 2.496RT + 1.499IFSS + 1.068BNA + \epsilon_{it}$$

From the regression results, for Hypothesis One (Ho1), on ROE, the value of t-calculated (2.661) is greater than its t-critical (1.98) and the p-value of 0.009 is

less than 0.05. Hence, the Null Hypothesis One is rejected, which means that there is a significant influence of RT (ATM) on ROE. For Hypothesis Two (Ho2), on IFSS, the values of t-calculated of 4.244 with p-value of 0.000 and t-critical of 2.00 were obtained. The t-calculated is greater than its corresponding t-critical (1.98) and p-value is less than 0.05. The Null Hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant influence of IFSS on ROE. For Hypothesis Three (Ho3), on BNA, the t-calculated was 3.009 is greater than the t-critical of 2.00 and p-value is less than 0.05 ($0.003 < 0.05$). The Null Hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant influence of BNA on ROE.

Discussion of the Findings

Hypothesis One was tested and the result from the regression analysis showed that Robotic Technology (measured by ATM costs) has a significant negative influence on corporate performance (ROE). This is confirmed as the p-value (0.009) for the influence of RT on ROE is less than 0.05 level of significance. The t-calculated of -0.181 indicated that Robotic Technology (ATM) has negative significant influence on corporate performance (ROE). The result obtained collaborates with the view of Jegede (2014). The author opined that, the deployment of ATMs terminals has averagely negative effect on the performance of Nigerian banks because of the alarming rate of ATM fraud and unreliable of bank network. In summary, it means that, the more the firms' investment in RT (ATM), the lesser the corporate profitability in terms of Returns on Equity (ROE). This could be so due to incessant fraudulent activities, unreliable of bank network, power challenge, security issues especially in some remote areas, increasing agency banking such as Point of Sale (POS) among others.

Hypothesis Two was tested and the result showed that there is a significant positive influence of intelligent financial supporting systems (IFSS) on corporate performance (ROE). This is confirmed as the p-value (0.000) for the influence of IFSS on ROE is less than 0.05 level of significance. The t-calculated of 0.333 indicated that intelligent financial supporting systems (Hardware and software/intangibles assets) have positive significant influence on corporate performance (ROE). This result is in support of the study of Agarwall *et al.* (2021). This is so due to its assistant in banking operations - online as well as offline operations as well as in and outside the banking hall.

Hypothesis Three was tested. The result of the empirical analysis also showed that Bank Network and Apps (electronic banking have significant positive influence on corporate performance (ROE). This result is in support of the study of Tunay, *et al.* (2018) that found that electronic banking technologies influence various performance indices of the bank.

Hypothesis Four was tested. The result of the empirical analysis also showed that Artificial Intelligence (proxied by robotic technology costs, intelligent financial supporting systems costs as well as bank network and apps costs) has significant positive influence on corporate performance (ROE). This is confirmed as the p-calculated (0.000) for the aggregate influence of AI Costs on ROE is less than 0.05 level of significance. This is confirmed as F-calculated of 20.802 is greater than F-critical of 2.43, meaning that, there is significant positive joint influence of Artificial Intelligence on Returns on Equity of the deposit money banks in Nigeria. This agreed with the views of Odoh *et al.* (2018) that found that Artificial Intelligence has significant positive influence on profitability.

5 Conclusion and Recommendations

The study aimed at examining the Artificial Intelligence Costs – Robotic technologies (ATM costs), intelligent financial supporting systems costs and bank network and apps/POS costs on Corporate Performance (proxied by profitability, ROE) of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria from 2011 to 2021. A composite regression model was used to analyse the data for the study and results revealed that:

- i. Robotic Technology (measured by ATM costs) has a significant negative influence on corporate performance (ROE);
- ii. Intelligent financial supporting systems (proxied by Hardware and software/intangibles assets costs) have positive significant influence on corporate performance (ROE).
- iii. Bank Network and Apps/POS (e-banking) have significant positive influence on corporate performance (ROE).
- iv. Artificial Intelligence Costs (proxied by Robotic technology costs, Intelligent financial supporting systems costs as well as bank network and apps as well as POS costs) have significant joint positive influence on corporate performance (ROE).

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that investment in

Artificial Intelligence in the deposit money banks (proxied by Robotic technology costs, Intelligent financial supporting systems costs as well as bank network and apps/POS costs) has significant joint positive influence on corporate performance (profitability, ROE). Thus, Artificial Intelligence technologies – ATMs, Intelligent financial supporting systems (Hardware and software/intangibles assets) electronic banking apps as well as POS are predicted to be the key determinants of improved corporate performance in deposit money banks in Nigeria.

On the basis of the conclusion, the following recommendations are made;

- i. The deposit money banks should invest more on improved and digital artificial intelligence technologies such as POS, telebanking, internet banking, banking apps, card data/ smartcard/electronic purse and other electronic banking technologies that is void of incessant fraudulent activities, unreliable of bank network, power challenge, security issues especially in some remote areas among others. Banks should stop investing more on ATMs because of the operational costs burden on the banks' profitability.
- ii. Banks should strive to increase their security apparatus to subvert the tricks of web scammers, limit the amount which customers may be allowed to withdraw at a time and alerts given on every transaction as well as encouraging customers more on e-banking/ banking apps. More awareness should be created to customers and bank clients.
- iii. Deposit money banks in Nigeria should invest more on agencies banking apparatus especially in the remote areas and bullet proof vans and stringent security should be used for every cash collection and mob-up outside the banking premises.

References

- Andriosopoulos, D., Michalis, D., Panos, M. P. and Zopounidis, C. (2019). Computational approaches and data analytics in financial services: A literature review. *Journal of the Operational Research Society*, 70(10), 1581-1599.
- Agarwall, H., Das, C. P. and Swain, R. K. (2021). Does Artificial intelligence influence the operational performance of companies? A study. *Atlantis Highlights in Social Sciences, Education and Humanities*, 2(1), 59 – 69.
- Bizarro, P. A. and Dorian, M. (2017). Artificial intelligence: The future of auditing. *Internal Auditing*, 5, 21 - 26.
- Dongre, N., Pandey, A. & Gupta, O. P. (2020). Artificial intelligence in accounting: Opportunities and challenges. *Journal of Xi'an University of Architecture & Technology*, 7(2), 1858 - 1864.
- Epps, R. W. and Cereola, S. J. (2008). Do institutional shareholder services (iss) corporate governance ratings reflect a company's operating performance? *Critical Perspectives on Accounting*, 19 (1), 1138 - 1148.
- Gotthardt, M., Koivulaakso, D., Paksoy, O., Saramo, C., Martikainen, M. and Lehner, O. M. (2019). Current state and challenges in the implementation of robotic process automation and artificial intelligence in accounting and auditing. *ACRN Oxford Journal of Finance & Risk Perspectives*, 8, 31-46.
- Greenman, C. (2017). Exploring the impact of artificial intelligence on the accounting profession *Journal of Research in Business, Economics and Management (JRBEM)*, 8(3), 1451-1454.
- Idekwulim, P. C. (2014). Teach Yourself Group Account (Fully IFRS Complied). Yaba (Lagos): Piccas Global Concept: 575 - 576.
- Ifurueze, M. S., Odessa, J. O. and Ifurueze, P. C. (2014). Impact of aggregated cost of human resources on profitability: An empirical study. *Journal of Business and Management*, 3(2), 30-40.

- Oriobe, G. and Akinyede, O. (2017). The effect of financial technology services on customers satisfaction in Nigeria. *SSRN Electronic Journal*, January, 1-9.
- Jegede, C. A. (2014). Effects of Automated Teller Machine on the Performance of Nigerian Banks. *American Journal of Applied Mathematics and Statistics*, 2, (1), 40-46. DOI: 10.12691/ajams-2-1-7.
- Losbichler, H. and Lehner, O. M. (2021). Limits of artificial intelligence in controlling and the ways forward: a call for future accounting research. *Journal of Applied Accounting Research*, 22 (2), 365-382. DOI: 10.1108/JAAR-10-2020-0207.
- Mutende, E. A., Mwangi, M., Njihia, J. M. and Ochieng, D. E. (2017). The moderating role of firm characteristics on the relationship between free cash flows and financial performance of firms listed at the Nairobi securities exchange. *Journal of Finance and Investment Analysis*, 6 (4), 1 - 3.
- Odoh, L. C., Echefu, S. C., Ugwuanyi, U. B. and Chukwuani, N. V. (2018). Effect of artificial intelligence on the performance of accounting operations among accounting firms in south east Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 7(2), 1 - 11.
- Solaimani, R., Rashed, F., Mohammed, S. and Elkelish, W. W. (2020). The impact of artificial intelligence on corporate control. *Corporate Ownership & Control*, 17 (3), 171 - 178 .
<http://doi.org/10.22495/cocv17i3art13>.
- Stancu, M. S. and Duțescu, A. (2021). *The impact of the Artificial Intelligence on the accounting profession, a literature's assessment*. Sciendo, 749 – 758. DOI: 10.2478/picbe-2021-0070. Proceedings of the 15th International Conference on Business Excellence 2021.
- Talan, G., Sehrawat K and Sharma, G. D. (2017). The relationship between human resource expenditure on staff and firm's performance: Case of SANDP BSE SENSEX 30 companies. *Global Journal of Enterprise Information System*, 2(1), 59 - 65.

-
- Tunay, N., Yiiksel, S. and Tunay, K. B. (2018). The effects of technology on bank performance in advanced and emerging economies: An empirical analysis. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 12 (1), 1 – 21.
- Wamba-Taguimdje, S-L., Wamba, F. S., Kamdjoug, J. R. K. and Wanko, C. E. T. (2020). Influence of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on Firm Performance: The Business Value of AI-based Transformation Projects. *Business Process Management Journal*, 1 (1), 1 – 45. DOI: 10.1108/BPMJ-10-2019-0411.
- Zhang, Y., Xiong, F., Xie, Y., Fan, X. and Gu, H. (2020). The impact of artificial intelligence and blockchain on the accounting profession. *IEEE Access*, 8, 110461-110477. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3000505>